

Radial and axial stiffness of superconducting bearings based on YBCO single-domain bulks processed with artificial holes

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Abstract

Superconducting magnetic bearings are becoming more widespread, due to the unique properties they provide. Their efficiency is unparalleled, there are no issues such as contact, friction, and wear. They require low or minimal maintenance, no lubrication and they work under extreme conditions (cryogenic temperatures, high vacuum). In this contribution, the influence of geometric properties of superconducting bulks on the performance of superconducting bearings was studied. The main focus was paid to load capacity, radial and axial stiffnesses. Two samples with a significantly higher aspect ratio compared to conventional bulks were prepared. One of these samples was synthesized with artificially created holes. The samples were prepared using top-seeded melt-growth process with an additional source of a liquid phase in the form of an underlying pad. The original thickness of 16 mm of the samples with a diameter of 28 mm was repeatedly ground down. Levitation force and trapped field were measured after each grinding step. Using this approach, the dependence of properties of the bulks on their thickness, scaling of these properties with thickness and the influence that artificial holes can make on the properties of finished single domain bulks were studied. The maximum levitation force was greatly improved for bulks with thicknesses of 2–6 mm. Such data is of the utmost importance in the field of superconducting YBCO single domain bulk ceramics, as it allows for better understanding and further improvement of both the manufacturing process and real-world applications of these materials.

Keywords: YBCO, superconducting bearings, radial stiffness, axial stiffness, artificial holes

(Some figures may appear in colour only in the online journal)

Introduction

Mechanisms provided with superconducting bearings present particularly attractive properties: they do not present contact between moving parts, they do not suffer from wear, they present a very low friction coefficient and they are particularly suitable for vacuum and cryogenic environments. In such environments, issues related to frictional surfaces in classical

mechanisms are particularly important and drastically limit the equipment lifetime. Therefore, superconducting instruments are a very promising solution in fields like high-speed bearings [1–4], aerospace [5–7], space engineering [8, 9], energy storage [10–14], wind turbines [15–18], systems or cryogenics [19–23].

In order to make the technology more competitive, optimization of the superconducting bearing design is

required. One of the very key features is to optimize superconducting bearings so it maximizes the force and stiffness while, at the same time, minimizes the amount of superconducting material [24]. The superconductor frequently drives many different design parameters of the entire mechanism such as weight, cooling power or maximum load capacity. In addition, the improvement of the mechanical properties such as the Young Modulus or ultimate strength are demanded to support the operational loads with a safety margin. Relative fragility and propensity of YBCO bulks to cracks difficult the design and can dramatically compromise safe operation of the equipment.

In order to maximize the levitation force of a superconducting bearings, many techniques have been proposed [25]. One of them consists of manufacturing some drills on the superconductor before the Corresponding phase [19]. One of the suggested benefits of such technique is to improve the chemical properties of the superconductor: both by facilitating the oxygenation of the sample during the oxygenation step and by reducing the porosity of the bulk, since the gas trapped in the samples' core can now be easily evacuated. Both facts could potentially result in improved levitation and mechanical properties of the bearings. Recently, the improvement of the mechanical properties of drilled superconducting samples have been demonstrated [26]. An improvement of about 45% of the Young modulus and the ultimate tensile strength between 15% and 20% have been reported.

However, whether the drills benefit the levitation properties or not is not yet fully clear. In 2004, Noudem *et al* demonstrated that the critical current, and therefore the magnetic flux trapped, can be highly improved by drilling some holes in the SCs before the oxygenation process [19]. Later in 2015 Dias *et al* [27] claimed a slightly improved trapping flux and levitation force capacity of drilled superconductors bulks. On the other hand, different studies have shown the opposite: a reduction of the trapped flux and the critical current [28, 29].

Theoretical study of the optimum disposition of the holes in a superconducting sample was published by Lousberg *et al* [30]. Different analytical and numerical results are presented for the magnetization drop for a cylindrical sample simple with different drills lattice they concluded that a triangular lattice (like the one used in the superconductors tested in this work) minimizes the magnetization drop due to removal of superconducting material.

In all previously reported works, studies have focused on the analysis of the levitation force but no attention has been paid to other critical parameters for stable levitation. In this paper, we present the experimental results of the levitation force and stiffness of a drilled cylindrical superconductor at different heights. The superconductor presents a large aspect ratio and an optimized drill lattice according to [30]. Additionally, the dissipated energy for quasi-static motion loops caused by magnetic hysteresis at 77 K is also reported. Results are then compared with identical superconductor with no artificial holes manufactured in the same conditions.

Experimental

The following chemicals were used for the synthesis of the cuprate precursor: BaCO₃ (99+, Sigma-Aldrich), Y₂O₃ (99.99%, Lachema Brno), CuO (p.a, Sigma-Aldrich). The initial powders were mixed and homogenized in the elemental ratio corresponding to Y_{1.8}Ba_{2.4}Cu_{3.4}O_x. Precursor powder was prepared by conventional solid-state reaction. The raw materials were mixed together and calcined in batches about 30 kg. The calcination was done in four steps at temperatures of 850 °C, 860 °C, 870 °C and 880 °C with intermediate homogenization.

A special 'spiked' tool was designed and manufactured to enable the direct pressing of pellets with holes. 80 g of YBCO powder was pressed uniaxially into discs of diameter of 32 mm using the 'spiked die' with holes of diameter 1.1 mm and an average hole to hole distance of 5 mm prior to melt processing. The tool consists of 13 spikes, one in the middle and rest in 2 concentric circles, spaced out evenly. This tool was based on triangular polar lattice used in past experiments which were designed based on the theoretical model mentioned in the introduction by Lousberg *et al* [30]. The goal is to allow the maximum amount of oxygen to be released from the bulk's volume, which in turn should improve the microstructure by reducing the number of defects. It also enhances the oxygen annealing and the heat exchange with the cooling liquid. On the other hand, a high amount of artificial holes or inadequate geometry can lead to a significant decrease in mechanical properties or lower trapped magnetic flux field, both of which would be highly undesirable and are to be avoided. A reference batch of discs without holes was also prepared for purposes of comparison. Each single grain was fabricated by using top-seeded melt-growth process (TSMG) in air under isothermal processing conditions using commercial thin films of Nd-123 on MgO (2 × 2 mm) as single crystal seeds. Additional liquid source was placed under the green body (12 g of mixture 28.4 wt% Y₂O₃, 2.4 wt% BaO₂ and 69.2 wt% Ba₃Cu₅O₈). Fragments of pre-sintered Y-211 phase covered by Yb₂O₃ were used as substrates underneath the pressed pellet to avoid an undesired nucleation. Fine-tuned temperature profile was developed to avoid formation of macroscopic cracks and nucleation of secondary grains. The large, single grains were then annealed in flowing oxygen between temperatures 300 °C–450 °C for 200 h.

Both samples, with artificial holes and standard, were machined to height of 18 mm and diameter of 28 mm and will be further referred to as 'STD' for the standard and 'H' for the sample with artificial holes. This abbreviation is followed by the number, which corresponds to the actual thickness in millimeters, following this series: 18, 16, 14, 12, 10, 8, 6, 4, 2 and 1, respectively. This is clearly shown in the figure 1.

The levitation properties were measured using in-house build test bench based on PT4000-50 kg load cell with an accuracy of ±0.1 N and 24 bit ADC Data Acquisition system (by Iowa Scaled Engineering). The permanent magnet (NdFeB, N52, $d = 25$ mm, $h = 25$ mm) was used to measure the levitation force. All presented measurements were taken

Figure 1. Diagram of YBCO bulk during the grinding process.

under liquid nitrogen conditions at 77 K. The speed of magnet was constant at 0.5 mm s^{-1} for all directions. The absolute error in displacement measurements was 0.1 mm. The combined errors were calculated for all stiffness values and are in their appropriate figures. Radial stiffness was calculated as a slope of force versus displacement curve (measured data was linear for the range measured). The axial stiffness was calculated as an dF/dc where F stands for force and c for displacement in the direction of the c axis. Local stiffness values provided in figures 5 and 6 were calculated from the 2 mm field cooling for a displacement value of ± 2 mm in radial direction in the case of the radial stiffness and 5 mm field cooling for a displacement value of ± 3 mm in the case of axial stiffness. Figure 2 shows a photograph of measurement setup with a detailed description.

The trapped field values were measured by a scanning Hall probe technique. Samples were field-cooled at the excitation field about 1.5 T. The maps were measured at a distance of about 2 mm from the sample surface in LN₂. The Hall probe scanner was manufactured and calibrated at CAN SUPERCONDUCTORS.

Results and discussion

Two bulks with the most similar properties were chosen. Standard and a sample with artificial bulks, which were successfully prepared and ground down repeatedly, without introducing any visible cracks or imperfections. The photos of samples with a thickness of 18 mm, 4 mm and 1 mm can be seen in figure 3.

The conical shape of the trapped field (see figure 4) confirm, that the bulks were single domain without any

Figure 2. Photograph of measurement setup with a detailed description used for stiffness measurement.

significant imperfections. The trapped field measured by a handheld probe was 1.33 (STD) and 1.28 (H) on the top side of the bulk. 0.68 and 0.64 measured on the bottom of the bulk for STD and H series respectively. The data is in good agreement with our observations during each grinding step, as the 3D maps show no measurable cracks or other significant imperfections in bulks themselves.

Figure 5 shows the force versus distance curve under zero-field conditions. The results show, that the presence of artificial holes did not influence the levitation force in 18 mm samples (this is also consistent with the levitation force data, which can be found in table 1). The shape of the curve is very similar for H and STD series. The maximum levitation force was 94 N at contact.

The dependence of radial stiffness on sample thickness can be seen in figure 6 (2 mm field cooling distance and maximum displacement). The presence of the artificial holes in the H samples did not influence the radial stiffness of the bearing. The most significant observation was, that the maximum of radial stiffness lied between 6 and 12 mm bulk thickness. Bearings with lower thickness simply did not contain enough material to resist the radial force to the same degree. If the thickness exceeds 12 mm the diminishing returns of the increase in thickness exceed the extra material gained by the increase in thickness. Furthermore, with the increase of sample thickness, added material is further and further from the magnet the influence of the increase in thickness is, therefore, less and less significant, as the force is inversely proportional to the distance squared.

In contrast to the radial stiffness, the axial stiffness was significantly influenced by the introduction of artificial holes

Figure 3. Samples with thickness (from left to right) 18 mm, 4 mm and 1 mm (compared with 1 EURO coin).

Figure 4. 3D trapped field maps of samples STD18 and H18 (at 77 K).

Figure 5. Force versus distance curve for zero-field cooling conditions.

(see figure 7). At lower thickness, this difference was very significantly pronounced, especially at 2 mm, where the values for H and STD were 10.5 N mm^{-1} and 7.7 N mm^{-1} respectively. As the sample thickness approached 6 mm, the difference in axial thickness shrinks and was relatively constant at $11\text{--}12 \text{ N mm}^{-1}$. The relative difference above 6 mm is insignificant. The improvement in axial stiffness attributed to the improvement in microstructure, caused by the release of oxygen out of the bulk's volume during the TSMG process. The stiffness was calculated at 3 mm distance (5 mm field cooling distance).

The hysteresis curves at the field cooling at 5 mm can be seen in figure 8. Maximum force achieved was 46 N for H2 sample at 5 mm field cooling and 33 N for STD2 sample at 5 mm field cooling. This showed, that the presence of artificial perforation series provided better results throughout the displacement of the samples, which the curves clearly demonstrate.

Figure 9 shows the dissipated energy, by magnetic hysteresis, for a quasi-static motion loop of $\pm 25 \text{ mm}$ total displacement from the zero-field cooled position at 77 K. The dissipated energy is normalized to the maximum value of force (see table 1). The value of the dissipated energy for samples containing artificial holes seems to be relatively lower than the standard samples in thickness range 6–2 mm. This can potentially result in a reduced friction coefficient and damping factor of the perforated sample with regard to the standard one.

Let us also note that the thin samples are interesting. The most impressive being the H2, whose axial stiffness was almost on par with samples up to 18 mm while using the fraction of the material, thus weight. It also had approximately 60% radial stiffness compared to the best performing STD10 and H10. This was achieved at the expense of dissipated energy.

Furthermore, the samples with a thickness of 1 mm showed remarkable similarity in all the properties measured. This fact is consistent with our results, given that the presence of artificial holes provides an improvement in microstructure by giving the oxygen a way to exit the bulk. As the 1 mm samples were the top part of the respective bulks during the TSMG, the presence of the artificial holes is unnecessary

Table 1. Levitation force (N) under zero-field cooling conditions for standard and perforated 'H' series.

	1 mm	2 mm	4 mm	6 mm	8 mm	10 mm	12 mm	14 mm	16 mm	18 mm
STD	23.1	47.6	71.5	83.7	88.6	89.9	88.8	91.7	87.9	93.6
H	23.5	55.8	84.9	88.0	90.0	89.3	90.4	97.6	90.5	92.6

Figure 6. Radial stiffness versus sample thickness.

Figure 8. Field cooling curves (samples with 2 mm thickness, Field cooling at 5 mm).

Figure 7. Axial stiffness versus sample thickness (field cooling at 5 mm, stiffness calculated at 3 mm distance from cooling position).

since there is a simple way for the released oxygen to escape in the direction of the c axis.

Conclusions

In this work, we have successfully prepared thick, single-domain YBCO bulks, with and without artificial holes. Two

Figure 9. Increase of dissipated energy with decreasing thickness (area normalized to the maximum value of force).

bulks with most similar properties (at 18 mm thickness) were chosen for this study to observe the differences during the thickness reduction. These bulks were gradually ground down up to 1 mm thickness without cracking. Zero field and field cooled levitation properties were measured after each thickness reduction. Radial and axial stiffnesses and the hysteresis area were calculated using the data obtained. We have shown that the radial stiffness is not affected by the artificial holes in any thickness region and the optimal thickness with the highest radial stiffness of the bulk is in region of 6–12 mm.

This is a surprising result and we would like to encourage any researchers to follow up on our contribution and explain this effect in detail. In contrast, the axial stiffness was almost constant down to 6 mm thickness ($11\text{--}12\text{ N mm}^{-1}$) and then starts to fall rapidly with further thickness reduction. The decrease was much faster in case of standard disk. The axial stiffness of 2 mm thin bulks was 10.5 N mm^{-1} and 7.7 N mm^{-1} for bulk with and without artificial holes, respectively. The maximum improvement (introduced by artificial perforation) in levitation force was observed for samples with thickness between 2 and 6 mm. We also observed the exponential increase of the hysteresis loop area (based on zero-field cooling measurements) which corresponds to dissipated energy during the cycle. The normalized dissipated energy was constant down to 8 mm thickness and then starts to rise with thickness reduction. The increase was slower in case of bulk with artificial holes. These results will be very useful for further design of YBCO bulks.

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